

ISic3441

I.Sicily inscription 3441

Language

Latin

Type

Honorific

Material

marble

Object

statue base

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lilybaeum

Place of origin (modern)

Marsala

Provenance

'nella corte della casa Lipari'

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Marsala

Physical Description**Dimensions**

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout**Execution**

Engraved

Letter Forms**Letter heights:**

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text**Apparatus****Translation****Commentary****Digital identifiers:**

TM 492389

EDCS 34700077

Bibliography

Henzen, W., Zangemeister, K. F. W. 1872-1913. *Ephemeris epigraphica. Corporis inscriptionum Latinarum supplementum*, edita iussu Instituti archaeologici Romani. Berlin. At VIII 696

Di Stefano, C.A. 1984. *Lilibeo. Testimonianze archeologiche dal IV sec a.C. al V sec. d.C.*. Palermo. At 146

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic3441. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4388586>